

MURRAY, Roseana. **Armarinho mágico**. Illustrations Christiane Mello e Fernanda Morais. São Paulo: Estrela Cultura, 2018.

REVIEW¹

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Roseana Murray is a renowned poet who has a perfect grasp of the rhythm and magic of words. In this book she recaptures the memory of her father's notion store, which sold everything from toys, fabric and clothes to thread and mirrors. Poems are richly illustrated by Christiane Mello and Fernanda Morais from Estúdio Versalete. Murray is the recipient of many awards, including those of APCA, FNLIJ in the Best of Poetry category (on four occasions), and Prêmio ABL for Best Children's Book. She has also been awarded FNLIJ's Highly Commendable laureate.

Keywords: Affection. Affective memory. Poems.

¹ Synopsis of the book for the Catalog Of The Children's Book Fair 2019 Bologna. Books published in 2018 and reviewed in 2019. Review and English version: Gisele Dionísio da Silva

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